

PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article reveals the essence of some pedagogical aspects of developing the competence of future teachers.*

Keywords: *competence, professional competence, competence, pedagogical competence, education, professional activity, cognitive component, professional skill.*

Introduction. Today, teachers and psychologists put forward many innovative ideas as methodological aspects and tools of the educational process. Because educational tools, methods and technologies play a leading role in ensuring its quality. Their use in specific conditions, assessment of pedagogical effectiveness, advantages and disadvantages of each method or technology directly and indirectly affect the quality of education. Such approaches are important not only for teachers, but also for students as a means of developing cognitive activity. At the same time, didactic means, methods and technologies act as the main tools for the development of students' cognitive abilities. Because the quality of this tool determines the quality of education. Today, the approach to students as users of cognitive tools is unusual for traditional pedagogy [1, 11].

Main part. From the reforms in the field of education carried out in our republic, it can be noted that our various scientific research on training the rising young generation as mature specialists in higher educational institutions creates new opportunities for us, young scientists. In the field of pedagogy, various scientific research is carried out with the aim of making future teachers masters of their subject, for example, to present to the public the development of artistic and aesthetic competence of future teachers in the field of fine and applied arts. Conducting scientific research makes it possible to train young personnel as mature specialists.

Nowadays, in the field of pedagogy, educational problems based on the competency-based approach are widely studied. Scientists such as R. Safarova, B. Mukimov, F. Robbimova, M. B. Urazova, U. M. Imomova, Sh. Kh. Khodzhaev, N. Yu. Volgina, N. Chomsky, R. P. Milrud. theoretical foundations for the implementation of the competency-based approach.

In linguistics, the term "competence" was first used by N. Chomsky in the middle of the 20th century and was interpreted as a set of knowledge, skills and competencies focused on activities in the process of using language, and by his followers this was interpreted as a competency-based approach. At the same time, the concepts of competence and competency-based approach are noted as factors indicating effectiveness in education, and their level is determined [2,23].

According to R.P. Milrud, "competence is a special area of activity in which a person demonstrates a mastered strategy for achieving a high level." He also expressed experience as actions carried out with the aim of gaining strategy, skills and practical knowledge on how to act in various spheres of existence based on existing knowledge and continuous self-improvement [3;71].

Scientists such as B. Mukimov, F. Robbimova used the concept of competence to solve professional problems associated with teaching specialized subjects, which represent preparation for changes in the labor market and innovation, as well as the skills necessary for a specialist to carry out effective activities in a certain area is defined as a requirement for educational preparation [4,5;16,18]. Researcher Sh. Kayumov gives the author's definition of the concept of "competence" as follows: professional competence is a set of personal and professional characteristics (knowledge, skills, abilities, professional abilities) in the professional and creative activities of a teacher in the educational process [6.] ;15].

Based on a generalization of various approaches to clarifying the structure of competencies, N. Yu. Volgina notes that most authors distinguish cognitive and individual-personal components. Typically, the cognitive component is considered by most authors as the formation of a knowledge system associated with the theoretical and methodological foundations of a certain field of science, however, from the point of view of the competence approach, the cognitive component is defined as the ability to apply theoretical knowledge in practice; it is appropriate to recognize the formation of skills, the ability to make decisions in standard and non-standard situations [7].

M.B. Urazova suggests dividing competencies into the following types from the point of view of project activities:

- Reflective competence: the ability to evaluate oneself, specify the moments and shortcomings of one's personality and activities, understand the reason for one's creative achievements and failures;

- Cognitive competence: the ability to independently acquire new knowledge and skills, apply ideas for independent development;

- Information competence: acquisition of special skills in obtaining, processing and using the necessary information;

- Communicative competence: methods that help achieve high-level communication;

- Social competence: understanding the social significance of reality, the ability to take responsibility, demonstrating the connection between personal interests and the needs of society [5;17]

As part of the experience and research conducted in our republic, we analyzed a number of views and opinions of researchers and scientists regarding this term. In particular, professional competence was defined by researcher G. Ernazarova and others as part of their scientific research: professional competence is the acquisition by a specialist of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for professional activity, and their practical application at a high level. Professional competence does not mean the acquisition by a specialist of individual knowledge and skills, but the assimilation of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction [8; 12].

According to R.P. Milrud, competence is the ability to work effectively by mastering success strategies based on acquired practical knowledge and developed skills. Therefore, the modern understanding of competence includes a person's ability to use his capabilities and perform certain functions, as well as the presence of mental states that allow him to act independently and responsibly" [3;71].

B. Mukimov, F. Robbimova expressed the concept of competence as the acquisition by a person of competencies related to the subject of activity, basic, interdisciplinary, general professional and specific field of science [4,5; 16-18].

The ability to withstand strong competition in the global labor market requires each specialist to have professional competence and consistently improve it. American psychologist

and researcher of human motivation David McClelland, at the beginning of the competency-based approach to an organization, institution or company, states that “when studying human personality, a candidate or employee does not answer correctly about his professional activities, a competent approach to working with employees Selection is aimed at assessing, training and development. It is clear that the employee has the appropriate professional competence.

The term “Professional Competence” is explained as follows: “This is the ability of an employee to act in accordance with the requirements of the position”: Professional competencies can be described as personal characteristics, for example, “Stress resistance”, “Stress resistance”. Ability to work in a team”, “Creativity” competencies, as well as acquired skills can also be demonstrated, for example: “Negotiations”, “Business planning” competencies [8; 11-17].

Pedagogical competence according to U.M.Imomova and B.Mukimov is a systemic phenomenon, the teacher’s abilities influence his competence. The effectiveness of the influence of a teacher’s personality on the learning and development of his students is determined by the level of his authority and presupposes the purposeful organization of the process of pedagogical communication and personal development and improvement of the teacher. He emphasized that in most cases, in the most general terms, competence is understood as a sufficient level of qualifications and professional skills of a specialist teacher[4;27].

In a scientific study conducted by researcher Sh. Qayumov, he gives the author’s definition of the concept of “competence” as follows: Professional competence is a professional ability that reflects the content of a teacher’s professional and creative activity. Professional competence is a concept that denotes an entire system, and professional competence is its component [6;13].

As B.Kh. Khodjaev rightly emphasized., in the pedagogical community, the process of determining competencies and competencies, which of them is considered basic (universal), methods of their formation and assessment is proceeding at a rapid pace, and intensive discussions are underway to clarify these concepts.

Result. Based on scientific studies and opinions expressed by the above-mentioned scientists and researchers, we have defined our author's opinion on the terms competence, professional competence and competency as follows:

Competence (from the Latin word “*competo*”, meaning “attain, fit, fit”) refers to the professional set of specific knowledge, skills and qualifications acquired by future teachers. is a requirement for the educational training of a specialist necessary for effective activities in the professional field.

Professional competence is the ability of a future teacher to improve his professional skills and qualifications, be able to analyze himself, master styles of professional communication and behavior, make rational decisions in problem situations (in the event of pedagogical conflicts, do, have). correct movement skills. The components of professional competence include:

- formation of student motivation;
- Knowledge of ICT;
- innovations in the educational environment;
- excellent knowledge of your subject;
- knowledge of one of the foreign languages;
- have pedagogical and psychological knowledge;
- work on yourself;
- ability to skillfully organize the educational process.

Future teachers who possess the above components will have knowledge of professional competence.

Competence is the professional knowledge acquired by future teachers, the ability to achieve consistent growth, improve their level, develop a critical and creative approach, improve the pedagogical process, have a positive impact on all participants in the educational process, and demonstrate their abilities. internal opportunities in professional activities.

Summary. Based on the above pedagogical definitions, the concepts of “competence”, “professional competence” and “competence” are closely related to each other and represent a type of professional activity that has been formed over the years. To develop the competence of future teachers, it is formed using various approaches, knowledge, skills and qualifications related to professional activities.

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